

MODAL VERB THEORY IN ENGLISH

Madrakhimova Dilrabo Jobilovna

11th School of Almalyk city of Tashkent region

English language teacher

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Abstract. This article contains information on the theory of modal verbs in modern English.

Keywords: Modal verbs, analysis, determination of lexical meanings, syntactic-semantic aspect, theoretical and Practical Grammar of the English language.

ТЕОРИЯ МОДАЛЬНЫХ ГЛАГОЛОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ

Аннотация. Данная статья содержит информацию по теории модальных глаголов в современном английском языке.

Ключевые слова: модальные глаголы, анализ, определение лексических значений, синтаксико-семантический аспект, теоретическая и практическая грамматика английского языка.

Modern English modal verbs are a comprehensive study of theoretical and practical aspects, as well as syntactic-semantic. To implement this goal, we set ourselves the solution of the following tasks:

1. Review and react to cases of “can” and “to able” in modern English;
2. To study their theoretical and practical meanings, taking a creative approach to existing points of view;
3. to have to give recommendations on their structure based on the study of the modal verb “must “by analogy with independent and auxiliary verbs;
4. Determining the role and place of modal verbs in sentence construction;
5. A thorough study of the syntactic and semantic properties of modal verbs using examples from works of art by modern English and American writers.

The methodological basis of the scientific work is that if there is a comparative and Comparative Study of modal verbs here with each other, the method of study is to state that in modern English and mainly in American English, modal verbs are used through comprehensive abbreviations. It is the science of the study to identify its various lexical meanings through analysis and to find alternative variants of their Uzbek language when translating the statements in which these statements are involved. The practical significance of this scientific work the materials given for the subjects of theoretical and Practical Grammar of the English language have scientific value, which can be used to write scientific articles on the topic of modal verbs in different directions for example: poetry, story, work, informative, English grammar can be used in practical training on this topic.

The novelty of this scientific work is that it shed light not only on probability, necessity, but also on the fact that in modern English, especially in colloquial language, modal verbs are spoken in the current American English language, adapting them to abbreviations or dialects. Being able to use each of the Modal verbs at a time in which they lie a fundamental meaning, has also given wide coverage of learning them, not replacing their place with each other. A special place among the equivalents of Modal verbs is occupied by research “Can”, “Could”, “To able

to”, “Need”, “May”, “Might”, “Must”, “Should”, “to have to”. Kaushanskaya touches on the following: “Modal verbs are used to show the speaker's attitude toward the action or state indicated by the infinitive, I. e. they show that the action indicated by the infinitive is agreed as possible, impossible, probable, improbable, obligatory, necessary, advisory, doubtful or uncertain, etc. The modal verbs are: can (could), may (might), must, should, ought, shall, will, would, need, dare. The modal expressions to be+infinitive and to have+infinitive also belong here”. “Modal verbs are called defensive because all of them (except “dare” and need) lack verbals and analytical forms” (I.e. compound tenses, analytical forms of the subjunctive Mood, The Passive Voice)“ J. In his textbook book “Grammar of the English language”, stormov also separately touches on the features of modal verbs: in his opinion, it is impossible to make an adjective form out of modal verbs. New verbs are not made from modal verbs using suffixes or prefixes, since modal verbs themselves are not made from other words using the word-formation method. Verbs that express compulsion, possibility, necessity, confidence, desire or permission, assumption, hypothesis, hand-to-hand and other similar meanings according to the meaning they mean are called modal verbs. Modal verbs differ semantically from other verbs due to the fact that they do not indicate action.

Modal verbs are always used together with the main verbs in the infinitive form, adding modal meaning to the main verbs. Gordon describes modal verbs as follows: “Modal verbs are defensive verbs since they many forms a modal compound predicate. They lack-s in the third person singular in the Present tense and have no verbs, so they have no analytical forms, some of them lack the form of the low tense”.

In conclusion, the teaching of modal verbs is considered significant from the point of view of today. For this reason, in today's scientific work, we tried to scientifically illuminate modal verbs.

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